

SPH prediction of energy dissipation in a sloshing tank subjected to vertical harmonic excitations

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Abstract—In [14], [16] the damping effect of sloshing flows on the dynamics of flexible structures was studied through an enhanced SPH model. Prediction of energy dissipation in these problems is of interest, among the others, in the aeronautic field to appropriately address sloshing-induced loads on aircraft wings. In the present work the same SPH scheme is applied and extensively validated on the experimental campaign performed in [25] in which a partially filled tank is subjected to harmonic vertical accelerations ranging from 0.5g up to 6g. Conversely to [14], in the present work long-time simulations are addressed spanning over more than 50 periods of oscillations. This approach allowed us to compare the predicted energy dissipation in terms of average value computed over several tank oscillations. The SPH scheme is tested over a large matrix of different frequencies and accelerations covering a wide range of flow regimes and spanning from mildly-deformed free surface to violent shaken flow. Even if the numerical model is only 2D and air phase is neglected, it is shown that the SPH solver is, in most of the cases, able to recover the experimental rate of dissipated energy with errors comparable to the intrinsic uncertainties of the problem. Considering that no parameter adjustment has been done in any of the performed test cases, this result makes the SPH a valid and competitive numerical solver for the simulation of such complex flows.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sloshing flows are those occurring when free surface waves are generated inside a tank and caused by any disturbance to partially filled containers. Depending on the type of disturbance and container shape, the liquid surface can experience different types of motion including simple planar, rotational, symmetric, asymmetric, quasi-periodic or chaotic. On the other hand, sloshing flows can be effectively used to dampen the oscillations of a structure. Tuned Liquid Dampers (TLD) exploit the liquid sloshing motion in a tank in order to counteract the external forces and dissipate energy. These dampers are of great interest in many engineering fields, spanning from the control of building stability or the rolling motion of ships in the civil engineering, to aerospace where the suppression of spacecraft instabilities is of fundamental importance during the ascent or landing stages [1], [12].

From the physical point of view, the study and prediction of the energy dissipation induced by a free-surface flow is generally arduous, especially in presence of wave breaking. [23] presented a review of studies dedicated to the dissipation

caused by wave breaking. From a numerical point of view, several methods have been used to evaluate energy dissipation in breaking waves. As far as SPH modelling of sloshing flows is concerned, in [5] and [6] a dynamical system involving a driven pendulum filled with liquid was studied experimentally and numerically by Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), focusing on the mechanical energy dissipation of the system.

Recently, kerosene containers placed inside aircraft wings have received attention as a complex industrial sloshing problem [9], [11]. During flight, sudden strong gusts accelerate the wing tips up to values of 10g, which results in sloshing amplitudes comparable to the tank dimensions and frequencies higher than 5 Hz (see [10]). This fluid motion, which several experiments have demonstrated to play a role on the damping of the wing vibrations, is significantly different from typical sloshing flows: the fuel is continuously broken into several jets and drops, whilst violently slamming alternately upward and downward against the tank walls.

In [7], [14], [16], such a violent flow has been numerically studied by reproducing the experiments in [17] in which a partially filled tank was subjected to a decaying vertical oscillating motion. The rapidly decaying flow motion on one hand allows one to perform short time simulations but, on the other hand, introduces difficulties in assessing the energy dissipation without solving the full fluid-structure interaction problem (for more details see [14]).

In order to overcome those limitations, in the present work the experiments by [25] are considered. In that experimental campaign a purely harmonic vertical motion is imposed on a partially filled tank. This approach makes possible to evaluate energy dissipation as an average values over multiple oscillation cycles, thus providing a more robust and reliable validation of the adopted SPH solver for this kind of flows, also in terms of convergence analysis. A large test case matrix spanning several motion frequencies and amplitudes has been tested. Further, the relevance of aspects such as surface tension and 3D effects are analysed and discussed, thus extending the findings in [14].

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The experimental testbed of the present analysis is a box tank made in Plexiglass with a height of $h = 27.2$ mm and base of sides $l_1 = 117.2$ mm and $l_2 = 78.0$ mm that is illustrated in figure 1. The dimensions are chosen in order to be able to trigger fluid slamming with the tank roof after an initial transient stage.

The tank is placed over a controlled electrodynamic shaker able to impose vertical sinusoidal displacement from a lower frequency of 5 Hz and able to reach 25 mm peak-to-peak displacement amplitude. The dynamic load at the interface between shaker and tank is measured by two PCB 208C03 load cells, placed in the middle of the long side of the tank base. Sloshing forces are determined by summation of two load cell signals, from which the inertial force of the non liquid mass upon the load cells must be subtracted. The system is also equipped with two redundant PCB 352C22 accelerometers placed at the opposite corners of the tank upper closing side and with a control accelerometer used by the shaker sine-sweep controller. The comparison between the data of the accelerometer used for sine-sweep control and the other two over the tank roof confirmed the considered experimental testbed rigidly behaved throughout the tests carried out.

The identification of the sloshing forces is carried out under sine-sweep excitation regime at constant acceleration. The curves showed in figure 2 illustrate the paths of the frequency-amplitude pairs run through the sine-sweep tests. The frequency sweep rate is 0.5 octave per second meaning that the frequency sweeps from 5Hz to 20Hz in 240s . This time is sufficiently long with respect to the period associated to the related oscillations to consider negligible the transient from a state to another. On the other hand the tests were performed at ten different value of accelerations from $0.25g$ to $6.0g$. It is worth to notice that the frequency-amplitude paths of higher acceleration tests in figure 2 not necessarily follow iso-acceleration curves since the electromechanical shaker is limited in providing at most 12.5mm of displacement amplitude.

Figure 3 provides a snapshot of the test at $a_0 = 3.0g$ of acceleration amplitude, when the frequency of the oscillation is $f = 13\text{Hz}$. The method developed in [25] allowed to identify a dissipated energy map in the considered frequency-amplitude range as shown in the colormap of figure 2. In the present research the SPH model is used to simulate sloshing flows under forced periodic tank motion considering a single pairs of frequency and acceleration, $f - a_0$, or equivalently frequency-displacement, $f - w_0$ in the map in figure 2.

III. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In the present work a three-dimensional fluid domain Ω is considered with its boundaries which are composed by the tank walls $\partial\Omega_B$ and the free surface $\partial\Omega_F$. The flow evolution is

Figure 1. Experimental set up.

Figure 2. Frequency-amplitude pairs spanned during different sine sweep tests to identify a dissipated energy map.

Figure 3. Snapshot of the sloshing flow at $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13\text{Hz}$.

governed by the Navier-Stokes equations (see also [14], [16]):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u}), & \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \mathbf{g} + \frac{\operatorname{div}(\mathbb{T})}{\rho} \\ \frac{De}{Dt} = \frac{\mathbb{T} : \mathbb{D}}{\rho}, & \frac{D\mathbf{r}}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}, \quad p = f(\rho) \end{cases}$$

where D/Dt represents the Lagrangian derivative, \mathbf{u} the flow velocity, \mathbf{r} the position of the material points, ρ the fluid density, e the specific internal energy, \mathbb{T} the stress tensor, \mathbb{D} the rate of strain tensor and \mathbf{g} the gravitational acceleration. The thermal conductivity is neglected and the liquid is assumed to be Newtonian. Differently from [16], in the present work the surface tension is included since Weber number can be rather small for test cases characterised by low-acceleration and high-frequency.

Eq. (1) can be either solved in an Inertial Frame of Reference (I-FoR) where the tank is moving or in a Non-inertial Frame of Reference (Ni-FoR) moving with tank motion. Although the description of the phenomena in both frames of reference does not affect the evaluation of the energy dissipated during the liquid motions, different numerical approaches may lead to different numerical errors, depending on this choice. Due to its easier implementation the Ni-FoR was adopted in the present work.

As for the liquid medium, the pressure p is assumed to depend only on the density. Furthermore, since a weakly-compressible condition is assumed, a simple linear equation of state can be adopted $p = c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0)$ where c_0 plays the role of a constant speed of sound of the liquid and ρ_0 is the density at the free-surface (where p is assumed to be equal to zero). In order to avoid too small time steps, c_0 is always set lower than its physical counterpart (in the present work, about two orders of magnitude lower). As discussed in [15] and in [18], in the weakly-compressible regime the energy dissipation linked to the water impacts using equation (1) is consistent with the one predicted by incompressible flow models.

IV. NUMERICAL SCHEME

In this section the SPH numerical model adopted is briefly recalled. In this work the quasi-Lagrangian SPH model with constant mass and Riemann stabilization terms presented in [19] is adopted. The governing equations (1) are discretized according to the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics numerical approach as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dV_i}{dt} = V_i \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \Theta_{i,Rie}^V + \\ \quad + V_i \sum_j \left[(\delta \mathbf{u}_j - \delta \mathbf{u}_i) - \frac{\rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \delta \mathbf{u}_j}{\rho_i} \right] \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{d(V_i \rho_i \mathbf{u}_i)}{dt} = -V_i \sum_j (P_i + P_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + V_i \rho_i \mathbf{f}_i + \Theta_{i,Rie}^{V\rho u} + \\ \quad + V_i \mathbf{F}_i^V + V_i \mathbf{F}_i^\sigma + V_i \sum_j (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_i + \delta \mathbf{u}_i, \quad \rho_i(t) = m_i / V_i(t), \quad p = c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where the index i refers to the considered particle and j refers to neighbour particles of i . The vector \mathbf{F}_i^V and \mathbf{F}_i^σ are the forces due to viscosity and surface tension acting on the particle i , while $\delta \mathbf{u}$ is the Particle Shifting velocity field which regularizes the spatial distribution of the particles during their motion. The mass m_i of the i -th particle is assumed to be constant during its motion. The particles are set initially on a Cartesian lattice with spacing Δr , and hence, the volumes V_i are initially evaluated as Δr^2 and Δr^3 , respectively in 2D and in 3D. The spatial gradients are approximated through the convolution with a kernel function W_{ij} . Following [3], a C2-Wendland kernel is adopted in the present work. The kernel radius, R is equal to $4\Delta r$ and $3\Delta r$, respectively in 2D and in 3D. The time derivative d/dt indicates a quasi-Lagrangian derivative, since the particles are moving with the modified velocity $(\mathbf{u} + \delta \mathbf{u})$. Because of this, the continuity and the momentum equations contain terms with spatial derivatives of $\delta \mathbf{u}$ (for details, the interested reader is referred to [4]). The Particle Shifting law $\delta \mathbf{u}$ adopted is the one presented in [21].

The term $\Theta_{i,Rie}^V$ and $\Theta_{i,Rie}^{V\rho u}$ are the numerical diffusive term introduced by [22] and further discussed in [19]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta_{i,Rie}^V &= -V_i \sum_j \left[\frac{\rho_R (\mathbf{u}_j + \mathbf{u}_i - 2\mathbf{u}_R) + \rho_L (\mathbf{u}_j + \mathbf{u}_i - 2\mathbf{u}_L)}{\rho_R + \rho_L} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{ij} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2 \frac{P_R - P_L}{c_0 (\rho_R + \rho_L)} \right] \mathbf{n}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \Theta_{i,Rie}^{V\rho u} &= V_i \sum_j \left[\frac{\rho_R (P_i + P_j - 2P_L) + \rho_L (P_i + P_j - 2P_R)}{\rho_R + \rho_L} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2 \frac{c_0 \rho_R \rho_L (\mathbf{u}_R - \mathbf{u}_L) \cdot \mathbf{n}_{ij}}{\rho_R + \rho_L} \right] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j. \end{aligned}$$

The viscous force \mathbf{F}^V is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^V := K \sum_j \mu \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)}{\|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i\|^2} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad (2)$$

where $K := 2(n + 2)$ being n is the number of spatial dimensions and μ is the fluid viscosity. As for the surface tension force, \mathbf{F}^σ , the model presented in [26] is adopted which is written in the form of a continuous surface force:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^\sigma := -\sigma \kappa \mathbf{n}_i \delta_{\Sigma,i} \quad (3)$$

where σ is the surface tension coefficient, κ the curvature at the interface, \mathbf{n}_i the unit vector normal to the interface and $\delta_{\Sigma,i}$ an interfacial function. This method has proved to be accurate even in single-phase approximation; the interested reader can find more details in [26].

V. CONSIDERATIONS ON THE ENERGY DISSIPATION

Following the analysis performed in [16], the energy balance for the particle system can be applied also to the numerical scheme (1). For the sake of brevity, only the main terms are briefly reported in this section. The SPH energy balance can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathcal{E}}_M + \dot{\mathcal{E}}_C = \mathcal{P}_V + \mathcal{P}_N + \mathcal{P}_{ext} \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{E}_M is the mechanical energy of the particle system, formed by kinetic energy \mathcal{E}_K and potential energy \mathcal{E}_P . Within the weakly compressible regime, the elastic energy term \mathcal{E}_C is generally negligible in the energy balance; hence it is not considered in the following discussion.

The external power \mathcal{P}_{ext} exerted by the tank walls on the fluid is evaluated through the mutual interaction between fluid and solid particles, as detailed in [2] and in [8]. The power related to the viscous forces contains the quantity \mathcal{P}_V which refers to the resolved viscous scales. Finally, the term \mathcal{P}_N takes into account the effect of the numerical diffusion related to Particle Shifting terms and Riemann stabilization terms (see [19] for more details). In the present work no explicit modeling of turbulent scales is introduced, as done in [14], as the Riemann solver can be regarded also as an implicit LES model [13]. This assumption will be verified as part of the model validation.

The discrete form of the energy dissipated, \mathcal{E}_{diss} , can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{E}_{diss} = \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_{diss} d\tau, \quad \mathcal{P}_{diss} := \mathcal{P}_V + \mathcal{P}_N \quad (5)$$

where t_0 is the initial time instant of the simulation. It is worth noting that even in the discrete form \mathcal{E}_C , \mathcal{P}_V , \mathcal{P}_N are invariant when switching the reference frame from inertial to non-inertial and vice-versa.

Integrating in time the energy balance (4) between the time instants t_0 and t we obtain:

$$\mathcal{E}_M(t) - \mathcal{E}_M(t_0) = \mathcal{W}_{ext} + \mathcal{E}_{diss}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{W}_{ext} is the vertical work exerted by the liquid on the tank. Note that in purely periodic motions, such as the ones considered in the present work, equation (6) can be simplified as:

$$-\mathcal{W}_{ext} \approx \mathcal{E}_{diss}. \quad (7)$$

This simplification is possible here since after the initial transient regime, the differences in mechanical energy between two periods are null in average. This means that, following the discussion in [16], in the Ni-FoR the dissipated energy can be directly evaluated as:

$$\mathcal{E}_{diss} = \int_{t_0}^t \mathcal{P}_{NF} dt = \int_{t_0}^t \int_{\Omega} \rho \mathbf{f}_{NI} \cdot \mathbf{u} dV d\tau, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{f}_{NI} are the non-inertial accelerations.

VI. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section the SPH simulations of the experimental test cases described in section II are presented. In figure 4 an overview of all the simulation conditions is represented in the frequency-displacement space. The acceleration amplitude of the performed simulations ranges from 1.5g up to 6g. Convergence analyses were also performed for the red dots represented in figure 4. In the same figure the energy dissipated in the experiment is represented as a blue contour map in order to show the distribution of most dissipative test cases. Since

Figure 4. Overview of the test-case matrix of numerical simulations performed in the $f-w$ space. Red and green dots represent the conditions considered for the SPH simulations; red ones are simulations for which also a convergence analysis was performed.

Non-Inertial Frame of Reference was adopted, a sinusoidal volume force corresponding to the frequency and acceleration amplitude of each specific test case was applied. An initial ramp of about 5 periods was added to avoid generation of shocks due to the sudden application of the volume force.

As for the boundary conditions, no-slip conditions are enforced at the walls since the flow Reynolds number, $Re = \frac{\omega w_0 h}{\nu}$, where $\omega = 2\pi/T$ being T the oscillation period, ranges between 3000 and 20000. This viscosity levels are of the same order of the oil test cases in [14] for which boundary layer influence was considered not negligible.

The simulation time was 65 periods for each test case. Dissipated energy in the experiment was measured through the evaluation of the work done by external forces \mathcal{W}_{ext} following eq. (6) whereas in the simulation it was more convenient to directly evaluate it integrating non-inertial forces as in eq. (8). In figure 5 an example of the obtained dissipated energy curve is shown. In order to obtain the average value of the energy dissipated per cycle, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$, and the related standard deviation, $\sigma_{\mathcal{E}}$, the curve was discretised with constant time intervals equal to the tank motion period T (blu squares in figure 5). Then $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss}$ was obtained as the average of the work done by non-inertial forces in each period:

$$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{diss} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\int_{kT}^{(k+1)T} \mathcal{P}_{NF} dt}{N}$$

In the following the number of periods considered is $N = 50$ since the initial transitory stage, estimated as the first 15 periods, was discarded from the average calculation.

Figure 5. Example of energy dissipated over 65 periods of oscillations (test at $a_0 = 1.5g$, $f = 13Hz$).

Figure 6. Initial evolution of the sloshing flow at $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$.

An example of the flow evolution is reported in figure 6 for the first impact against the tank ceiling. This occurs after about 8 oscillation periods for the case at $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$. The impact is the result of the progressive amplification of a standing wave that establishes at the beginning of the simulation forced by the oscillating vertical acceleration. From figure 6 drops at the tip of the fluid ejections are formed as a result of the surface tension acting at this length scale. The following evolution is a sort of sloshing flow which in [16] was denoted as "shaken flow". The fluid alternatively slams against the ceiling and the floor of the tank with production of several vortical structures and consequent dissipation of energy.

In figure 8 the non-dimensional vorticity field is shown for four different cases at the same time instant. The case with lowest kinetic energy among those, i.e. $a_0 = 1.5g$, $f = 13Hz$, exhibits very low vorticity levels and a rather compact fluid configuration. Conversely, both the cases at $a_0 = 3.0g$ are characterised by large fragmentation and a complex vorticity field due to the repeated flow impacts.

Figure 7. Convergence analysis for the case $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$. Left plot: time evolution of the dissipated energy for five different resolutions, namely $H/\Delta x = [12, 25, 50, 100, 200]$,

In figure 7 the results of the convergence study for only one case, $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$, are reported as example. For the convergence study a series of simulations with resolution $H/\Delta x = [12, 25, 50, 100, 200]$ was performed. The steepness of the energy curve is evidently converging as the resolution is increased. In the right plot of figure 7 only the computed \bar{E}_{diss} and the related standard deviation are shown as a function of the particle resolution. For this test a convergent value is clearly observed for both the average and standard deviation of the dissipated energy per cycle (as mentioned above, each average is computed discarding the first 15 periods of the entire time history). The rate of convergence varies with the resolution and is between 1 and 3. This is not always the case, as for some conditions more complex trends with non-monotonic behaviours were observed. However, for all the simulations considered in the present analysis a convergent result was achieved as very small differences were always found for the two highest resolutions tested, namely $H/\Delta x = 100$ and $H/\Delta x = 200$. For this reason the whole test-case matrix was then performed using the spatial resolution $H/\Delta x = 100$.

A. Comparison with experimental data

The comparison with the experimental data from [25] is firstly addressed comparing the numerical results in terms of average and standard deviation of the energy dissipated per oscillation cycle, namely \bar{E}_{diss} and σ_E . These data are available for the experimental test performed at $a_0 = 1.5g$ and $a_0 = 3.0g$. For the rest of the test matrix only the averages are available and will be shown later. In figure 9 the SPH average and standard deviation of the dissipated energy per cycle are compared to their experimental counterpart. For the cases at $a_0 = 1.5g$ a very good agreement, both in terms of average and standard deviation, is observed at all the tested frequencies. The SPH results are characterised by a slightly larger standard deviation but this feature is observed for all the test cases and will be further inspected in the next section. Note that for lower frequencies (that is, higher flow energy content) the standard deviation is significantly larger as a consequence of the more pronounced chaotic character of the flow.

As for the cases at $a_0 = 3.0g$ (right plot of figure 9 the

Figure 8. Comparison of the non-dimensional vorticity field for different flow conditions at the same time instant. Top-left plot $a_0 = 1.5g$, $f = 9Hz$; top-right plot $a_0 = 1.5g$, $f = 13Hz$; bottom-left plot $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 9Hz$; bottom-right plot $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$.

Figure 9. Comparison between experimental results and SPH simulation of the average value and standard deviation of the dissipated energy for the cases at $a_0 = 1.5g$ (left) and $a_0 = 3.0g$ (right).

comparison is generally less favourable. The standard deviation of the SPH solution is remarkably overpredicted. Interestingly, the experimental data exhibits a very small dispersion of the energy dissipation with respect to the cases at $a_0 = 1.5g$ even though the kinetic energy of the flow is generally larger. At this acceleration the flow is more stable as it regularly impacts against the ceiling at each oscillation. On the contrary, from bottom plots of figure 8 it is evident the distribution of the fluid is irregular and this is reflected also in a highly irregular evolution of the dissipated energy.

A comprehensive picture of the overall agreement between SPH and experiments is reported in left plot of figure 10: in this scatter diagram both experimental and SPH data are reported and coloured according to \bar{E}_{diss} . In this plot the values of \bar{E}_{diss} span over two orders of magnitudes and, therefore, it gives an idea of the capability of the SPH model adopted

to predict the energy dissipation in very different sloshing regimes. In fact, at low acceleration values and high frequency the kinetic energy content is small and surface tension effects become relevant. Conversely, at high acceleration and low frequency the kinetic energy content is large and the flow essentially impacts twice per cycle against the tank horizontal walls. In this case surface tension is less important and flow damping is driven by impacts.

However, in this plot it is not possible to precisely assess the error of the SPH solution with respect to the experiments, given the large scale of energy dissipation adopted. Therefore, in middle and right plot of figure 10 the contour of $\bar{E}_{diss}/(mU^2)$ are reported, where $U = \Omega w_0$ is the tank peak velocity. This number was also referred as the sloshing loss factor in [24], providing a measure of the dissipation for the kinetic energy provided to the tank. In the plots of figure 10

Figure 10. Comparison between experimental results and SPH simulation for the entire test-case matrix. Left plot: measured values of the dissipated energy \bar{E}_{diss} . Middle and right plot: contour plot of $\bar{E}_{diss}/(mU^2)$ for experimental data (left) and SPH results (right).

one can appreciate in which conditions the SPH model is able to accurately predict the experimental dissipated energy. In particular, a large underestimation (up to 25%) is observed for the cases characterised by accelerations higher or equal to $3g$ and frequencies lower than $15Hz$. In fact, these are the cases for which the kinetic energy is larger and, in this region, 3D effects could be relevant. This aspect is addressed in the next section.

B. Relevance of 3D effects

The relevance of 3D effects in the considered problem was addressed by performing 3D SPH simulations for few specific cases. Given the computational cost of such simulations, the particle resolution adopted is much coarser with respect to 2D cases and the number of performed periods was limited to about 10 periods after the initial transient. The simulations were performed with resolution $H/\Delta x = 25$, corresponding to about 770,000 particles in the domain. The kernel radius was reduced to $R = 2.7\Delta x$. In figure 12 the initial flow evolution is shown for the case $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$. In figure 13 the same plot of figure 9 is reported by adding also two solutions from 3D simulations, in the specific at $f = 13Hz$ and $f = 9Hz$. Remarkably, the 3D solution is closer to the experimental data, especially at $f = 9Hz$ where the 2D solution largely underpredicts the dissipated energy. This is in agreement with the findings in [20] in which 2D solutions give lower estimation of energy dissipation with respect to 3D.

Moreover, in the 3D solution a large decrease in the standard deviation is observed. The 3D flow is, indeed, more “stable” and less chaotic with respect to the 2D flow. This can be better appreciated looking the hysteresis cycles of the vertical force acting on the tank. In figure 11 the vertical force is plotted as a function of the tank displacement for experiment, 3D and 2D SPH solutions. The 2D solution exhibits a quite noisy pattern, which is result of the multiple impacts occurring in the flow. On the other hand the 3D solution is much smoother as the same impacts occur in the form of multiple quasi-cylindrical jets impinging against the horizontal walls, a process which is repeated cycle after cycle.

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Figure 11. Vertical force acting on the tank as a function of the tank displacement: comparison between experimental results (left), 3D SPH (middle) and 2D SPH (right) for the case at $a_0 = 3.0g$, $f = 13Hz$.

Figure 12. Free-surface configuration of an initial instant of the 3D SPH simulation at .

Figure 13. Comparison between experimental results and 2D and 3D SPH simulation of the average value and standard deviation of the dissipated energy for the cases at $a_0 = 3.0g$.

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